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**The Platform for Sharing, Initiating and
Learning Citizen Science in Europe**

Deliverable 2.4

EU-Citizen.Science Sustainability Plan

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Abstract	<p>The deliverable 'D2.4 EU-Citizen.Science Sustainability Plan' is developed under task T2.4 'Community and platform management' within WP2 'Platform, Community and Network Building' which is led by ECSA. This task and WP will culminate in the handover of the EU-Citizen.Science platform to ECSA for its maintenance and management after the end of the EU-Citizen.Science project. The specific objectives of this document are 1) to present a Sustainability Plan aimed at ensuring the maintenance and further use of the EU-Citizen.Science platform and its assets beyond the project's lifespan, 2) to share the collective reflective process that led to the creation of the Sustainability Plan, and 3) to recommend actions to sustain the Platform, enhancing the use and outreach of the Project results.</p>
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Version Log

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Definitions and Acronyms

API	Application programming interface
Data	Information, in particular facts or numbers, collected to be examined and considered as a basis for reasoning, discussion, or calculation. In a research context, examples of data include statistics, results of experiments, measurements, observations resulting from fieldwork, survey results, interview recordings and images. The focus is on research data that is available in digital form. (European Commission, 2016)
Dataset	A grouping of data
DoA	Description of Action
EC	European Commission
ECSA	European Citizen Science Association
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation

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H2020	Horizon 2020
HQ	Headquarters
JRC	Joint Research Centre, the European Commission's science and knowledge service
Metadata	A description of data
MoU	Memorandum of Understanding
PPSR	Public Participation in Scientific Research
Repository	A location in which data is stored or managed
SwafS	Science with and for Society
WG	Working group
WP	Work Package

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Executive Summary

The deliverable ‘D2.4 EU-Citizen.Science Sustainability Plan’ of the EU-Citizen.Science project is developed under task T2.4 ‘Community and platform management’ within WP2 ‘Platform, Community and Network Building’ which is led by ECSA, and is due in M34 (October 2021). This task and WP will culminate in the handover of the EU-Citizen.Science platform to ECSA for its maintenance and management for at least five years from January 2022, once the EU-Citizen.Science project has ended.

The aim of the EU-Citizen.Science project is to develop a sustainable platform that serves to act as a mutual learning space for citizen science, focusing on Europe but relevant globally. The overall vision for the EU-Citizen.Science platform is to aid the mainstreaming of citizen science in Europe, such that it becomes an appreciated and widely established means for the democratisation of science in Europe. To continue to maintain the Platform it is crucial that the Platform is technically and thematically (content-wise) sustainable.

The specific objectives of this document are 1) to present a Sustainability Plan aimed at ensuring the maintenance and further use of the EU-Citizen.Science platform and its assets beyond the project’s lifespan, 2) to share the collective reflective process that led to the creation of the Sustainability Plan, and 3) to recommend actions to sustain the Platform, enhancing the use and outreach of the Project results.

This deliverable details the process through which the Sustainability Plan has been developed, highlighting the collective reflective process – or methodology – carried out by ECSA and the EU-Citizen.Science consortium. It presents the stepping stones of the process that have led to the elaboration of a practical, forward-thinking and consistent plan that will ensure that the EU-Citizen.Science platform continues to function and expand as the citizen science hub in Europe and beyond under the leadership of ECSA. The Sustainability Plan consists of the collective reflection, a sustainability strategy which in turns includes cross-cutting recommendations, relevant dimensions of sustainability and the legacy of the EU-Citizen.Science project and its exploitation, and finally, a list of concrete actions. This document will be revised and updated regularly by ECSA staff.

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1 Introduction

The deliverable D2.4 ‘EU-Citizen.Science Sustainability Plan’ is structured along the following sections:

Section 1: *Introduction* gives an introduction to the EU-Citizen.Science project and explains the purpose of this deliverable – the development of a Sustainability Plan for the EU-Citizen.Science platform.

Section 2: *Sustaining the assets of the Platform* describes the assets of the Platform and the main functionalities that should be maintained. This section also provides definitions that inform sustainability in the context of an EU-funded project.

Section 3: *Methodology: a collective reflection to create the Sustainability Plan* introduces the journey followed to collectively develop the Sustainability Plan. Four big meetings are presented and their main results are summarised and clustered.

Section 4: *The Sustainability Strategy: Cross-cutting recommendations, dimensions and legacy* is structured in general cross-cutting recommendations, the five dimensions of sustainability identified and the legacy of EU-Citizen.Science. The latter presents exploitable project results and establishes current project tasks that need to continue to ensure Platform sustainability.

Section 5: *Sustainability Action Plan* presents a list of actions to sustain the Platform. This section also includes a selection of tasks that will be carried out until the end of the Project to ensure technical sustainability, a note on the handover to ECSA and considerations on challenges and threats in implementing the Sustainability Plan.

Section 6: *Conclusion* summarises the ideas presented in the document.

1.1 The EU-Citizen.Science Project

Citizen science broadly refers to “the general public engagement in scientific research activities when citizens actively contribute to science either with their intellectual effort or surrounding knowledge or with their tools and resources”¹. Citizen science actively involves the public in scientific research that generates new knowledge or understanding, and thus has the potential to bring together science, policy makers, and society as a whole in an impactful way.

Although citizen science as a practice has been around for centuries, the term citizen science was coined in the 1990s and has gained popularity since then. Recognition of citizen science is growing in the fields of science, policy, and education and in wider society. As a core dimension of Open Science, citizen science opens up the opportunity for all members of society to take an active role in research, innovation and the development of evidence-based policy, at local, national and EU

¹ Societize Project (2014) White Paper on Citizen Science for Europe. Available at: https://ec.europa.eu/newsroom/dac/document.cfm?doc_id=6913

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levels. Citizen science is establishing itself as a field of research and a field of practice, increasing the need for overarching insights, standards, vocabulary, and guidelines².

It is the ambition of the EU-Citizen.Science project (‘the Project’) to build on the growing impact of citizens participating in research across the full range of scientific enquiry, by developing a sustainable platform to act as a mutual learning space for citizen science, focusing on Europe but relevant globally. The overall vision for the EU-Citizen.Science platform (‘the Platform’) is to aid the mainstreaming of citizen science in Europe, such that it becomes an appreciated and widely established means for the democratisation³ of science in Europe, as shown in figure 1 below.

Figure 1: The vision, mission and objectives of the EU-Citizen.Science project

The building of the Platform has been pursued through three interconnected lines of activity:

1. Coordinating citizen science actions, and making use of existing resources in the presently fragmented citizen science landscape in Europe;
2. Engaging quadruple helix stakeholders at local, national and European levels;
3. Creating a mutual learning space and a set of comprehensive, co-designed training modules for different target audiences.

² Vohland, K., Land-Zandstra, A., Ceccaroni, L., Lemmens, R., Perelló, J., Ponti, M., Samson, R., Wagenknecht, K. (Eds.) (2021). The Science of Citizen Science. Springer International Publishing. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-58278-4>

³ Democratising science means “creating institutions and practices that fully incorporate principles of accessibility, transparency, and accountability. It means considering the societal outcomes of research at least as attentively as the scientific and technological outputs. It means insisting that in addition to being rigorous, science be popular, relevant, and participatory”. Guston, David H. “Forget Politicizing Science. Let’s Democratize Science!” Issues in Science and Technology 21, no. 1 (Fall 2004) https://issues.org/p_guston-3/

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In keeping with our mission, we have aimed to engage equally with citizen science participants, practitioners, researchers, policy makers and society as a whole throughout the course of the project. In order to do so effectively, a clear understanding of who our target audience is, their needs and requirements, and how we can build a community of engaged users of the Platform has been necessary.

1.2 The purpose of this deliverable

The deliverable ‘D2.4 EU-Citizen.Science Sustainability Plan’ of the EU-Citizen.Science project is developed under task ‘T2.4 ‘Community and platform management’ within WP2 ‘Platform, Community and Network Building’ which is led by ECSA, and is due in M34 (October 2021). This task and WP will culminate in the handover of the EU-Citizen.Science platform to ECSA for its maintenance and management for at least five years from January 2022, once the EU-Citizen.Science project has ended.

The aim of this document is to provide an actionable and coherent guide to support the sustainability of the EU-Citizen.Science platform over time. It presents previous, current and future sustainability actions for the long-term success of the EU-Citizen.Science platform. Under ‘the long-term success of the Platform’ we understand that the Platform continues to be in the position to achieve the vision, core mission and objectives of the Project laid out in the previous section (see figure 1).

What does sustainability mean in the context of the Platform? A factor at the heart of the Project’s mission statement, is that the Platform must be both *technically sustainable* and *thematically sustainable*. In order to achieve the first one, all the technologies used for development are based on open standards and published under free licenses. On the other hand, there is the need to provide sustainability mechanisms from a content point of view. Complementary to both these aspects, sustainability in this context also means to ensure the use of the Platform and its services by the internal and external stakeholders identified in D2.1 ‘Stakeholders, Network & Community Mapping Report⁴’ by maintaining the current features of the Platform, continuing to develop it and by promoting its use. Internal stakeholders are consortium partners and the citizen science community, and external stakeholders are organisations, institutions, users and policy-makers that will have a role in keeping the Platform active and user-oriented. Technical, thematic (content-wise), and financial sustainability as well as exploitation and engagement as the relevant dimensions of sustainability we have identified for the Platform are explained in section 4.2 of this deliverable.

As of 26th October 2021, the EU-Citizen.Science platform hosts 192 project profiles, 176 resources and tools, 17 training modules and 161 organisation profiles. The Project has organised and co-organised events and workshops with or aimed at the Project’s consortium, the citizen science community, the European Commission and other H2020 SwafS (i.e. Science with and for Society) funded projects, different audiences interested in learning more about citizen science, and representatives from ministries across Europe, among others; and the Platform has been presented in many events, conferences and festivals. Without being exhaustive, this constitutes the scaffold

⁴ D2.1 ‘Stakeholders, Network & Community Mapping Report’ is available at: <https://zenodo.org/record/3465726>

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of the European hub that the Platform aims to be. The process of building this European hub began in 2019, and during the last almost three years, the EU-Citizen.Science consortium has been able to set up a robust digital platform that hosts a wide variety of resources for the research, communication and practice of citizen science. Gaining loyalty and attention from the community is an endeavour that needs time and that evolves in time. It will keep unfolding under the guiding role of ECSA, who will leverage all the assets that EU-Citizen.Science has produced and gathered.

The current funding landscape presents challenges in supporting citizen science. Most schemes from national and European funders typically only provide short-term, fixed duration grants. There are very few national or international funding organisations that have dedicated, bespoke funding schemes to support the long-term sustainability of citizen science initiatives or projects⁵.

Hence, with this Sustainability Plan for EU-Citizen.Science we aim to ensure a continued use of the Platform by the citizen science community. This requires keeping a close look at and boosting communication with the end users; motivating them to participate and interact; and improving the Platform's features, considering the technological advancements of online digital spaces. Therefore, the Sustainability Plan for the EU-Citizen.Science platform entails the involvement of the consortium partners, through the commitment that all partners will continue to use and promote the EU-Citizen.Science platform and assets after the end of the project, and the engagement of other (external) stakeholders in using the Platform.

Objectives of this deliverable:

- To present a Sustainability Plan aimed at ensuring the maintenance and further use of the EU-Citizen.Science platform and its assets beyond the Project's lifespan;
- To share the collective reflective process that has led to the creation of the Sustainability Plan;
- To recommend actions to sustain the Platform, enhancing the use and outreach of the Project's results.

2 Sustaining the assets of the Platform

2.1 Description of the assets of the Platform

There have been three Platform releases so far – April 2020, September 2020 and January 2021 – and the final Platform release is planned for the end of October 2021⁶, coinciding with the submission of this deliverable. This subsection presents the current assets of the Platform and the

⁵ Pelacho, Maite, & Sanz, Francisco. (2021). COESO Deliverable 4.1: Landscape study on funding schemes for Social Sciences and the Humanities' Citizen Science activities (draft). Zenodo. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5137247>

⁶ The final platform release was originally planned for December 2021, the last month of the project. but has been advanced to the end of October 2021 to leave enough time after the launch to solve possible bugs and to promote the new release of the Platform more while the consortium still works together.

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main functionalities that will be developed until the end of the project (31st December 2021) and that should both be maintained.

An overview of the core structure of the Platform is shown in the following figure:

Figure 2: Modules up and running in the 2.5 and third release of the Platform (M28 and M34)

The assets of the Platform are described in what follows:

- **User's management and personal area.** Users can register, log in to or log out from the Platform as well as recover their password. There is a personal area where users can view/edit their profile, find their submitted projects, resources and organisations as well as the projects they follow and the resources added to their library for quick access. As part of the final launch of the Platform the personal area has been improved. Personal user profiles have been made public and searchable – thus encouraging networking – but closed by default and GDPR compliant. Users are able to see their submission history to easily search for and edit previous submissions. Linked organisations, of which they are a member, are also displayed.
- **Projects.** The Platform showcases a wide range of citizen science projects that have been undertaken in Europe, particularly those that are still active, which enables practitioners to establish their own professional networks, as well as find regional and national network associations that will be relevant to their practice. This enables the Platform to serve as a European meeting point for relevant actors in citizen science, as well as for newcomers interested in discovering its potential. It is possible to search through citizen science projects and filter according to various fields. A registered user can add projects that will have to go through moderation in order to be accepted (or not), and then appear on the Platform. The Platform community manager regularly reviews and approves new projects. Finally, users can write reviews, follow a project and edit their own projects.
- **Resources.** The resources section of the Platform, which is the mutual learning space, offers high quality materials for practitioners across all domains and experience levels. This section enables community-driven content sharing, where citizen science project

coordinators and participants can exchange experiences and successful strategies. Curation of these resources by the consortium partners (in ‘Our Gold Star Selection’ section) enables the promotion of outstanding, state-of-the-art tools and materials that further the implementation of best practice. The same functionalities available for projects are also available for resources. Uploaded resources go through a moderation process where quality criteria are applied.

- **Training resources.** Training resources and materials have a dedicated section on the Platform. These are resources that are designed or can be used explicitly for the goals of teaching or training a person on the practice of citizen science. The same functionalities available for projects and resources are also available for training resources. Uploaded training resources go through a moderation process where quality criteria are applied.
- **Profiles of organisations** that are involved in citizen science projects and research. Organisation profiles can be created and linked to uploaded projects and/or (training) resources.
- **Profiles of platforms or networks.** A section dedicated to citizen science platforms and networks has been launched with the last Platform release. Users can create platform or network profiles and link them to the profiles of involved organisations.
- **Moderation process and application of the quality criteria.** A quality criteria framework was developed within WP3 of the Project for defining and sharing state-of-the-art resources for conducting citizen science projects and initiatives in practice to ensure that the resources profiled on the platform are of good quality⁷. While initially developed for the assessment of resources, the more general quality criteria have been applied to projects and the criteria for resources can be applied to training resources. These criteria are applied in a moderation process carried out by the Platform community manager. All resources, projects and training resources on the Platform have gone through a moderation process considering impact and quality criteria to assess if they are about citizen science, relevant to citizen science and good quality. The moderation process has been streamlined by adding a mandatory text field to the submission forms that asks for a description of the citizen science aspects of the project or (training) resource to be submitted.
- **Training modules and Moodle integration.** The training modules featured on the Platform enable the acquisition of skills and competencies to overcome difficulties or challenges in setting up citizen science initiatives, such as choosing the optimum methodology, reflecting on expected outcomes and impacts, data quality assurance and validation, linking the various governance levels from local to global, ensuring balanced participation of citizens, the integrity of methods and data, recognising the work of citizens

⁷ Read more about the quality criteria framework in D3.1 ‘Framework report describing criteria and rationale for sharing and selecting state of the art citizen science resources’ and in D3.3 ‘Review of Framework Implementation Defined in D3.1’ on the Project available at <https://zenodo.org/record/3716236#.YWMO2t9CRhE> and <https://zenodo.org/record/5041332#.YWK5sd9CRhE>.

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participating in citizen science initiatives, and managing large numbers of volunteers. A Moodle integration provides a space for the training modules developed under WP5. Part of the Moodle integration is the possibility to log in to the EU-Citizen.Science Moodle with the log-in credentials of the EU-Citizen.Science platform.

- **Translations of the static pages and multi-language support.** The static parts of the Platform are available in English and have been partly translated into the 11 European languages⁸ of the consortium by members of the consortium. The languages displayed can be chosen by the user with a selector for easy change between languages. The final release of the Platform incorporates the option for the community of users to submit translations of the descriptions in projects, resources, etc.
- **API, interoperable metadata and collaboration with other citizen science platforms.** The API (application programming interface) of the EU-Citizen.Science platform allows interoperability and connection to other platforms. Metadata for projects follow the PPSR ('Public Participation in Scientific Research') core project metadata model. The metadata for resources and training resources follow the Dublin Core and the metadata for organisation profiles and platform profiles is our own. The API as well as all forms and metadata are standard and allow interoperability with other platforms. The API allows almost everything that the Platform allows: authentication, and to pull, push and edit content⁹. Currently, several collaborations with other national citizen science platforms are underway to connect EU-Citizen.Science with them via the API (see section 5.1 of this deliverable for more details on this). A new feature of the final Platform release is the possibility to submit profiles of other citizen science platforms (similar to the organisation profiles currently on the Platform). This will give more visibility to national citizen science platforms and make them easy to find on the Platform.
- **Blog posts** are also showcased on the homepage, providing news and updates about the Project, the Platform and the citizen science community at large.
- **Social media channels** of the Project and Platform include Twitter, Facebook, Instagram and a joint newsletter with other H2020 SwafS citizen science projects. A Platform digest with recently added content on the Platform is included in the final Platform release and will be sent out regularly.
- **An events calendar** to provide information on citizen science events all over Europe is also available.
- **Community forums** for questions, conversations, and collaboration with the rest of the community.

⁸ These languages are Dutch, Estonian, French, German, Greek, Hungarian, Italian, Lithuanian, Portuguese, Spanish and Swedish.

⁹ In this context, 'pull' means to pull content from another platform to show it on EU-Citizen.Science and to 'push' means to show content from EU-Citizen.Science on other platforms.

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- **Integration of the EU-Citizen.Science and ECSA memberships** to register to become a member of ECSA on the EU-Citizen.Science platform to increase traffic to the Platform and expand the community of users. This functionality will be finished by the end of 2021. ECSA members will return to the Platform more often to get to their account and check it regularly for updates and a habit of going to the Platform will develop. ECSA members on the Platform will have a badge (such as a small logo showing over their profile image) which will in turn strengthen the community by showing a certain level of expertise.

2.2 Definitions that inform sustainability in the context of an EU-funded project

The following three definitions inform our understanding of the sustainability of the Platform and help to contextualise it.

Sustainability refers to how things stay through time, they do not perish. A sustainability plan for a project is a guide to how a project, in this case, the Platform, plans to stay active over the long term. Such a plan usually covers financial health, community engagement and leadership.

Exploitation is defined by the European Commission as the use of EU-funded project results for commercial purposes or in public policy making. In the context of EU-funded projects, it means to make use of the project results in further activities, other than those covered by the project. Therefore, it is important that the project and its results have commercial, social and/or academic relevance and that they can be commercialised or exploited as a standalone result (product, process, service, etc.)¹⁰.

We consider it relevant to add a definition of the term advocacy, since it will be one of the recommended actions of the Sustainability Plan.

Advocacy: The term ‘advocacy’ is often used to describe an activity or process of “supporting a cause or proposal”¹¹ and especially gaining “public support”¹² for this activity or idea. The activity can be carried out either by an individual or group. Organizations describing their advocacy activities most commonly use the term to show how they create central positions and use them to influence positions of political, public or economic institutions, e.g. the bodies of the European Union. This process often takes place by including a broader public community, both from within the organizations and from without. The advocacy process often works in two directions: organizations include public opinion in their creation of central positions and strive to influence public opinion at the same time¹³.

¹⁰ Definition of the term ‘Exploitation’ in the Glossary of the European Commission’s Funding & Tenders Portal, available at <https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/portal/screen/support/glossary>

¹¹ Definition of the term ‘advocacy’ in the Merriam-Webster dictionary. Available at: <https://www.merriam-webster.com/dictionary/advocacy>

¹² Definition of the term ‘advocacy’ in the Cambridge Dictionary. Available at: <https://dictionary.cambridge.org/dictionary/english/advocacy>

¹³ Ernst, Elisabeth, Ekanger, Aysa, Franczak, Mateusz, Katsaloulis, Iraklis, Töpfer, Marlen, & Wnuk, Magdalena. (2021). How-to-advocacy: OPERAS practical guide on advocating for open scholarly communication in the social sciences and humanities. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5043438>

3 Methodology: a collective reflection to create the Sustainability Plan

Given the importance of the topic at hand, several sessions were planned to closely examine the sustainability of the EU-Citizen.Science platform and to make recommendations that would form the project's Sustainability Plan. The sustainability of the Platform has been addressed in different, smaller constellations in parallel to the bigger meetings outlined in the following pages. We have chosen to focus on these bigger meetings since they cover all the main topics and the smaller meetings mainly focused in detail on selected aspects that had already been raised.

The first meeting refers to a workshop that took place within the ECSA HQ in September 2020; the second meeting was held in February 2021 with the ECSA Board and ECSA policy officers involved in the Project; the third meeting was organised in the form of a session at the EU-Citizen.Science 3rd project meeting in April 2021; and the fourth meeting was scheduled in May 2021 with the ECSA Board and ECSA policy officers. The consolidated outcomes of these meetings are summarised further in the following subsection.

Figure 3: Overview of the process for setting up the Sustainability Plan

The approach followed to structure both the Sustainability Plan and the meetings to come up with it is illustrated in the figure above. In the journey to the Sustainability Plan for the Platform we started from the vision and mission of the Platform, Project and of ECSA, which nicely overlap and complement each other. This provided the **structure**; it helped to develop a clear frame and to think of the sustainability of the Platform: ‘What do we stand for?’ and ‘Where do we want to go?’. From there, the goal was to think in terms of **strategies** and to find creative and feasible ideas to shape what we want to achieve. Strategies contain a comprehensive and actionable plan, this Sustainability Plan – **solutions**. The next step in the journey is to implement the Sustainability Plan in the next few years and to review it yearly to achieve **success**.

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Figure 4 represents a roadmap of what we have called the ‘collective reflection’ to involve ECSA and its Board, EU-Citizen.Science consortium partners and other interested stakeholders in this process and reflect together (collectively) on the sustainability of the Platform.

Figure 4: Overview of the collective reflection process

3.1 Summary and overview of the main results of each meeting

In this subsection, table 1 provides an overview of the four meetings mentioned and the main goals. A summary of the discussion and results of each meeting is provided after the table. The goal of this subsection is not to go into detail on concrete ideas and actions that resulted from the meetings – these will be included in section 5 of the deliverable, the Sustainability Plan, which contains concrete actions and recommendations – but rather to give an understanding of how the thinking of sustainability of the Platform developed.

Table 1: Overview of the four meetings

Meeting	Attendants	Date	Main goal
1st meeting	ECSA HQ	30th September 2020	Reflect on the intersections and alignment between ECSA’s and the Platform’s vision and mission
2nd meeting	ECSA Board and	16th	Starting from the more abstract vision and

	ECSCA policy officers working for the Project	February 2021	mission of ECSCA and the Platform: How do we imagine the Platform of the future and how do we effectively bring the citizen science community to it?
3rd meeting	EU-Citizen.Science Consortium	20th April 2021	Brainstorm on different aspects related to sustainability and provide concrete suggestions for the dimensions of financial, technical and content/thematic sustainability
4th meeting	ECSCA Board and ECSCA policy officers, Ibercivis	18th May 2021	Build on the different inputs and agree on main foci of sustainability

a) 1st meeting: ECSCA Headquarters Team, 30th September 2020.

The aim of this meeting was to reflect on the intersections and alignment between ECSCA's and the Platform's vision and mission. This meeting gathered all project officers of ECSCA and its Managing Director, i.e. the ECSCA HQ members. The first part of the meeting developed around two main points: ECSCA today and ECSCA tomorrow. The rationale was to set the tone among participants so they could depict the strengths and opportunities that ECSCA currently offers and how these could be harnessed through synergies with the Platform. **ECSCA today** was described by its HQ members as a young organisation that is mainly funded by EU projects and that provides a space for networking with the wider community of citizen scientists, researchers and supporters. **ECSCA tomorrow** was described by its HQ members as an organisation that should maintain its collaborations with local networks, engage the users of the platform in a way that they see the value of it and push its further development, give voice to diversity, keep lobbying for more funding, constantly reflect on who is being excluded and how to remove current barriers, keep monitoring its reach and does not forget the scientists. ECSCA was described as an organisation that pays special attention to capacity building and collaborations at a local level.

After an introduction to the Platform, the second part of the meeting started with needs and expectations towards it: Do you feel like there is anything missing in the platform planned functionalities that should absolutely be included? If so, why? The next step was to think of ways of making the shared dream for the future of EU-Citizen.Science and ECSCA possible: What skills are needed? In-house skills or does it need to be externalised? What can the ECSCA team contribute to or take over?

b) 2nd meeting: ECSA Board. 16th February 2021.

This meeting was centred on how we imagined the Platform of the future and how we could effectively bring the citizen science community to it. This meeting gathered most of the [ECSA Board Members](#). The starting point was the inheritance of the EU-Citizen.Science platform by ECSA after the end of the Project – from January 2022 – and a reminder of the vision and mission of ECSA and of the Platform. The meeting could be summarised by the question ‘How do we imagine the Platform of the future and how do we effectively bring the citizen science community to it?’. The discussion was facilitated using two padlet boards. The first one was for envisioning the Platform of 2025 and opening the floor for ideas to come. The second board was for converging the ideas and seeing how to transform them into actions. The main topics discussed were: a) Involving users and intended audience: usability testing and user behaviour; b) Communication and marketing; and c) how to keep and establish new connections between members of the citizen science community and connections with local communities, institutions, platform users, and other platforms.

c) 3rd meeting: EU-Citizen.Science Consortium. 20th April 2021.

The third EU-Citizen.Science project meeting was a full-day event that took place on 20th April 2021. Session 2 was dedicated to Platform sustainability and led by WP2 leader, ECSA, and is what is referred to as ‘3rd meeting’. However, session 1 ‘Reflective stock-taking’ and session 5 ‘Dissemination of and engagement with the platform’ too provided input useful to the sustainability of the Platform. The main aim of the session dedicated to sustainability was to brainstorm on different aspects related to sustainability and provide concrete suggestions. By the time of this meeting, the first structure of this deliverable existed and three dimensions of the sustainability of the Platform had been identified: technical and thematic sustainability, as laid out in the DoA of the Project, and also funding or financial sustainability/aspects. The meeting started with a presentation of the session and its structure, was followed by work in groups in three breakout rooms – one per sustainability aspect – and finished with all participants together for a group discussion. This session gathered all 23 partners of the EU-Citizen.Science consortium, some members of the Advisory Board of the Project, and some representatives of other H2020 SwafS citizen science projects that had been invited to attend the EU-Citizen.Science 3rd project meeting. Each participant chose a thematic group to discuss in depth one of the three aspects or dimensions of sustainability mentioned. Participants were provided with Google Docs with already filled in suggestions that they could continue to fill in and comment. Questions to start the discussion and ideas they could debate were given.

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The main points and suggestions raised in each group are:

- Funding/financial: a) monetise the training resources; b) constantly apply for funding and micro-funding at the local and EU level; c) design paid consultation and training for niche stakeholders.
- Technical: a) provide infrastructure for national citizen science platforms and connect them to the Platform; b) improve site accessibility; c) ensure that the source code can be used by others by facilitating the introduction to the code, splitting it into modules and making the frontend easy to personalise.
- Thematic/Content: a) involve the community in ensuring that quality on the Platform is maintained but combine it with expert knowledge, i.e. continued moderation following the quality criteria developed; b) deploy proactive communication; c) engage with national citizen science platforms and ask them to check the projects they share on the Platform (which can happen in the long term, once the connection via the API is established and functioning).

d) 4th meeting: ECSA Board. 18th May 2021.

The main aim of this meeting was to build on the different inputs gathered until then – mainly the results of the previous workshop with the ECSA Board and the session on Platform Sustainability and the project meeting, that is meetings 2 and 3 – and to agree on the main foci of sustainability. This meeting gathered almost all [ECSA Board Members](#), ECSA policy officers and Ibercivis, as a third party heavily involved in the Project and developing the Platform. Two digital tools were used for sparking and facilitating the discussion: Miro and Padlet. The meeting started with a synthesis of the results of the previous two meetings and with an exercise to prioritise actions to be taken to connect to the different target audiences of the Platform and work towards Platform sustainability. From there, participants branched out to make their ideas more concrete and discussed the different paths that could be taken to sustain the Platform. The discussion revolved around three main topics: a) the incentives and benefits for users of the Platform, b) the connections that are needed to keep the Platform linked to different stakeholders and c) the communication plan needed to gain the loyalty of users and to bring new ones into the community.

3.2 Integrating and clustering meeting outcomes

The four meetings and their outcomes are reflections on the current position of the Platform and collections of the needs of the community, considering the diversity of perspectives and contexts. They feed into the sustainability strategy and Sustainability Plan. The outcomes of this reflective process are summarised in figure 5 below.

SUMMARY OF THE OUTCOMES OF THE REFLECTIVE PROCESS

Figure 5: Summary of the outcomes of the reflective process

The clustering of the outcomes from the meetings held among the different groups of interest have led to the establishment of the sustainability strategy and Sustainability Plan, which are explained and detailed in sections 4 and 5 respectively. The ideas and recommendations from the meetings can be clustered under the following overarching topics, which help to inform the sustainability strategy and can serve as guiding principles.

- **Keep connections: Networking and advocacy**
- **Keep motivation: Communications and community engagement**
- **Keep relevant: Content is key and user's feedback**
- **Keep moving: Exploitation and funding**

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4 The Sustainability Strategy: Cross-cutting recommendations, dimensions and legacy

“Good strategy involves not just prioritisation, but making a decision to really focus on certain issues”

Karin Laljani

A sustainability strategy provides a framework for focus, prioritisation and a clear plan of action. We have identified five dimensions of Platform sustainability: technical sustainability, thematic sustainability, financial sustainability, engagement and exploitation. The current section will provide a description of these dimensions; the concrete actions in the Sustainability Plan (in the next section) will be classified according to them. The sustainability strategy is structured in: general cross-cutting recommendations, the five dimensions of sustainability and the legacy of EU-Citizen.Science.

4.1 Cross-cutting recommendations

Before we turn to the cross-cutting recommendations, below are the vision and mission of ECSA and of the EU-Citizen.Science platform which complement each other, serve as guidance for the strategy and inform the cross-cutting recommendations.

ECSA’s vision: “Our vision is that all citizens in Europe are valued and empowered as actors in advancing knowledge and innovation, and thus supporting sustainable development. We want to establish citizen science as a recognized, promoted and funded approach, one that fosters scientific literacy and the democratization of science. Through this, we want to see an increase in the social relevance and sustainable impact of research, and a stronger evidence base for policy processes, in Europe and globally.”¹⁴

ECSA’s mission is to connect citizens and science; to promote sustainable development through citizen science; and to ensure that citizen science contributes to policy processes.

Vision and mission of the EU-Citizen.Science project and platform¹⁵

Our vision is that citizen science becomes an appreciated and widely established means for the democratization of science in Europe.

Our core mission is to be the European reference point for citizen science through cross-network knowledge sharing for citizen science participants, practitioners, researchers, policy makers and society across Europe.

Cross-cutting recommendations for ECSA’s taking ownership of the Platform

- Establish and maintain the excellence of the material, resources and projects showcased
- Foster permanent and broader coordination at national and European levels
- Ensure that the Platform is able to cater for a diversity of stakeholders with different

¹⁴ Vision and mission of ECSA available at: <https://ecsa.citizen-science.net/about-us/>

¹⁵ Vision and mission of the EU-Citizen.Science Project available at: <https://eu-citizen.science/about/>

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interests

- Give the community a sense of ownership of the Platform by harmonising and integrating their visions
- Keep the Platform as an open space and an innovation hub always in mind
- Set up effective ways of determining the wider social value of the Platform
- Create a framework that allows constant reflection, evaluation and iteration
- Search for alliances that can path the way for sustainable long-term funding

These cross-cutting recommendations are ideas we aspire to achieve and which should guide our actions to sustain the Platform in the next few years. Together with the premises of keeping connections and motivation and keeping relevant and moving presented in section 3.2, the cross-cutting recommendations will help us have a vision and both look forward towards the future of the Platform and think more broadly about ways of sustaining it – beyond the more immediate and concrete actions needed to keep the Platform running.

4.2 Dimensions of the sustainability strategy

The five dimensions of the sustainability strategy identified are presented in the following pages, starting with technical and thematic sustainability as already laid out in the DoA of the Project.

Technical Sustainability

The technical sustainability of the Platform covers all needed aspects to maintain a) the Platform online and in production, and b) the source code of the Platform up-to-date regarding new discovered bugs in used third party libraries and in the EU-Citizen.Science code.

The Platform has two main components, the Platform itself¹⁶, developed from scratch using Django 2.2, and the training platform¹⁷ where all training modules are hosted and deployed using Moodle. Both platforms are served using a [Nginx](#) web server. [Postgresql](#) is the database used in the Platform. [MySQL](#) is the database used in the Moodle training platform. All these services are hosted in a 4-cores 4GB virtual OVH server running Ubuntu 18.04 LTS. Database and filesystem backups are performed daily.¹⁸

To continue to sustain the Platform and keep it available, all these services (Postgresql, MySQL, Nginx and the operative system itself) need to be maintained in the latest stable and supported version. On the other hand, there are installed third party open-source programs (such as the Moodle learning management system) and libraries (such as all the needed python libraries for the Platform) that will need to be updated periodically (e.g. if a security vulnerability is found). Finally, the source code of the Platform will need periodical revisions (e.g. if a security vulnerability or bugs are found).

¹⁶ EU-Citizen.Science platform available at: <https://eu-citizen.science>

¹⁷ Moodle platform for EU-Citizen.Science available at: <https://moodle.eu-citizen.science>

¹⁸ For more details on the structure of the Platform refer to deliverable D2.3 'Platform Functionality Requirements & Specification Report' available at: <https://zenodo.org/record/3612808#.YWRZzN9CRhE>

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These actions are only the strict and necessary ones to maintain the Platform in production. New ideas or areas for improvement on the Platform that are worth addressing during the Platform's road to sustainability will surely appear during the next few years.

Thematic (content) sustainability

The Platform must also be thematically sustainable, i.e. sustainable from the content point of view. Content refers to projects, resources, training resources, organisations and platform profiles, training modules, events and blog posts. Therefore, content sustainability can be understood in two ways. On one hand is the question as to how can the content on the Platform continue to be up to date, e.g. that content remains valid or that links to other sites work. On the other hand we have to think about how we can continue to put (new) content on the Platform – in a sustainable way. By fostering active participation of the community we guarantee that the Platform has active contributors that populate it with new and current resources keeping it alive and current.

Financial sustainability

The aim here is to work towards rendering the Platform financially sustainable so the revenue produced can be reinvested in the maintenance (and future development) of the Platform. Considerations that fall within this dimension are: how can we generate an income stream with the functionalities that the Platform already has?; where is the 'market pain' (i.e. something that is missing and people are willing to pay for)?; are we aiming at institutions or individuals, and what kind of budgets do they have access to?

Exploitation

Exploitation is defined by the EC as the use of EU-funded project results in further activities other than those covered by the project. Using the project results for commercial purposes is part of these further activities. Under 'exploiting' the Platform and Project results we understand *using (or applying), maintaining, replicating*¹⁹ and *scaling* them (*up*). To scale up means to "increase the size, amount, or importance of something, usually an organisation or process"²⁰. In the context of projects and initiatives, *scaling up* often means to *expand* to other geographic, socio-economic, political or thematic areas, and *scaling* in this context means to *apply* or to *replicate* in other areas.

Project results that can be exploited are: the Platform and its content (e.g. the training modules) and functionalities; project deliverables and documents (e.g. policy briefs, reports) as knowledge base and representing best practice; methods and tools as concrete and tangible outcomes; capacity-building activities, communication channels and partnerships and synergies created during the Project. By being open source and catering for 12 languages we further contribute to the accessibility of the Platform contents despite cultural and financial barriers. The Platform contents have different formats (e.g. training modules, policy briefs, webinars, project profiles, events, organisation profiles, etc.) and focus on different topics of citizen science, thus catering for a

¹⁹ Some synonyms to replicate are: copy, duplicate, reproduce and clone.

²⁰ Definition of the term 'scale up' in the Cambridge Dictionary. Available at: <https://dictionary.cambridge.org/dictionary/english/scale-sth-up?q=scale+up>

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diverse set of needs and interests. All of these features increase the exploitability of the Platform. The next subsection on the legacy of the Project and Platform will expand on this.

Engagement

To engage with our target audience and get users of the Platform to use it and continue to contribute to its building a communication strategy and actions are needed. Within this dimension fall actions that will engage with the citizen science community, communicate with its members, involve them and foster ownership of the Platform. Through fostering ownership, the citizen science community is called upon to continue to contribute to its building and provide feedback to develop the Platform further – ultimately contributing to its flourishing: being sustainable and up to date. Actions within the engagement dimension will ensure the necessary visibility of the Platform both to the relevant audience and to potential future stakeholders so they can exploit the Platform (and its contents).

4.3 Legacy of EU-Citizen.Science

The legacy of the EU-Citizen.Science project are 1) Project results that can be exploited and disseminated beyond the lifetime of the Project (e.g. deliverables²¹), here called ‘exploitable results’, and 2) tasks or processes that need to continue or that are recommended to continue in order to sustain the Platform directly or assist in sustaining it (e.g. the moderation process for submissions to the Platform). The latter will be called ‘task continuity’ in this deliverable for the purpose of simplicity. There is overlap between part of what is contained in this subsection and in section 2.1 where the assets of the Platform were described. However, the legacy of the Project will be structured according to WP.

In addition to the five dimensions of the sustainability strategy identified, it is important to think of exploitable results and task continuity because they are the object/content to be sustained and exploited. Along these lines, the sustainability strategy is composed by: the cross-cutting recommendations – the *vision*; the dimensions of sustainability strategy – the *method*; and the legacy of the project – the *object/content*. The Sustainability Action Plan in the next section presents the *actions* to carry out the Sustainability Plan.

Note that the aim of the following table is not to be exhaustive and list all possible project results that could be exploited and all possible tasks and processes that could be maintained beyond the lifetime of the project. Having a strategy entails focus and prioritisation. Therefore, the project results, tasks and processes mentioned in this table have been identified as being those that will have the strongest impact on Platform sustainability.

²¹ All public Project deliverables are available at the zenodo community of the Project at: <https://zenodo.org/communities/eu-citizenscience>

Table 2: Legacy of each WP in relation to EU-Citizen.Science platform sustainability

Work Package	Legacy: Exploitable results and task continuity
WP1 Coordination and Management	Exploitable results and task continuity: Monthly SwafS citizen science meetings with RIA and EU-funded projects (T1.5)
WP2 Platform, Community and Network Building	Exploitable results: Platform and its content, community around the Platform, deliverables Task continuity: moderation process of submitted projects, checking submitted events, blog posts and profiles of organisations and platforms/networks, moderating the forum, community building, putting new content on the Platform, exchanging broken links, presenting the Platform at events
WP3 Content Framework, Quality Assurance and Curation	Exploitable results: quality framework for resources which is the basis for the moderation of submitted resources and can carry an important function in guiding and influencing how new resources are developed in the field (in the form of deliverables) Task continuity: moderation process for resources, submitting new resources to the Platform
WP4 Awareness and Engagement Public and Policy Makers	Exploitable results: deliverables on policy-maker engagement and awareness-raising activities
WP5 Training Needs Assessment, Creation and Delivery	Exploitable results: training resources, 20 training modules on Moodle designed for self-learning without a tutor and which have a good potential to run as part of a tutor guided session Task continuity: moderation of submitted training resources, exchange of broken links in the training resources, Moodle security alerts and software updates, ensure that training module content and URLs continue to work
WP6 Dissemination, Exploitation, and Strategic Communication	Exploitable results: social media channels (twitter, Instagram and Facebook accounts) and the newsletter Task continuity: maintain the social media channels and the newsletter
WP7 Evaluation and Impact Assessment	Exploitable results: deliverables on the evaluation and impact framework and the interim/final impact assessment, which include interviews with the Project consortium and give account of what has changed institutionally throughout the three years of the Project

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5 Sustainability Action Plan

A list of actions to ensure the sustainability of the Platform are presented in this section, the Sustainability Action Plan. The strategy followed to develop the Sustainability Plan culminates in this list of actions. It is important to point out that ECSA will take ownership of the Platform after the end of the EU-Citizen.Science project and therefore most of the actions mentioned in this section are directly addressed at ECSA. However, it is expected that the partners in the Project will have an interest in maintaining the Platform and continue to contribute to it since the Platform is an important instrument for advancing citizen science in Europe, and beyond.

It is worth mentioning that a lot of work has been done since the beginning of the Project towards the dimensions of the sustainability strategy, especially towards technical and thematic sustainability, by ensuring that the Platform and its content is created in a way that facilitates its sustainability by following standard metadata (PPSR core project metadata model for projects and Dublin Core for resource and training resources) and thus allowing interoperability with and connection to other platforms. Before turning to the list of actions, we dedicate a section on actions that we are currently doing and will do before the end of the Project thinking in terms of technical sustainability.

5.1 Tasks until the end of the Project to ensure technical sustainability

Before the end of the Project we will update all the needed python libraries, Moodle, and other services to the last stable version compatible with our configuration. Among other things (but not limited to) we will:

- Upgrade from django 2.2 to django 3.0
- Install the last stable of compatible versions of used python libraries
- Check for vulnerabilities using GitHub information
- Upgrade from Ubuntu 18.04 LTS to Ubuntu 20.04 LTS
- Install the last stable version of the Moodle platform and plug-ins

In addition, we are working towards the adoption of the Platform, the Platform source code, or some of the tools provided by the Platform by third citizen science communities. Increasing the community of users, adopters and developers (using our source code released under EUPL license) will ensure long-term sustainability of the Platform and the code.

We have defined four different types of collaboration with other (national) platforms:

- **Collaboration type 1 – Interest:** The platform has interest in knowing what is happening inside EU-Citizen.Science. The platform might ask for further information. EU-Citizen.Science will send information about platform development, platform structure, criteria, etc. The platform (if it technically exists) complies with (or undertakes to comply with) the agreed metadata (PPSR Core, schema.org, etc.).

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- **Collaboration type 2 – Share projects, resources and other datasets:** The (national) platform will share projects and resources with EU-Citizen.Science using the API or the other way around where the (national) platform will show projects and resources that are stored on EU-Citizen.Science. This collaboration type needs a developer on both sides.
- **Collaboration type 3 – Integration:** No national platform currently exists for that country, and EU-Citizen.Science will include national projects inside the EU-Citizen.Science platform.
- **Collaboration type 4 – Use our source code to install the platform:** EU-Citizen.Science will help to install the EU-Citizen.Science source code to host a new national platform.

The following table shows the platforms, networks or institutions that are working on connecting with the Platform or have expressed their willingness to use our Platform in one of the four defined collaboration types.

Table 3: Inter-platform collaboration

Platform name	Country	Collaboration type	Explanation / Status
Virtual Ecosystem for Research Activation – VERA H2020 COESO project	Belgium, France, Germany, Italy, Portugal, Spain ²²	2	It is planned that the VERA platform and the EU-Citizen.Science platform will connect through the API and exchange data in both directions.
Areas for co-operation through citizen science – ARCS Swedish national platform	Sweden	2	The Swedish platform was created using Wordpress CMS. A plug-in was created to store projects on EU-Citizen.Science and pull Swedish projects from EU-Citizen.Science. The last release of the Platform will provide the multilingual support needed by the ARCS platform.
science ensemble and Particip-Arc French citizen science platforms	France	2	Both French platforms plan to connect to the EU-Citizen.Science platform through the API to send French projects to EU-Citizen.Science. The French platforms need multilingual support to do so because one platform has projects in English and French and the other one only in French.

²² These are the countries where the partners of the COESO project are located.

Platform name	Country	Collaboration type	Explanation / Status
Citizen Science for the Amazon Network Amazon citizen science platform	Bolivia, Brazil, Colombia, Ecuador, France, Peru, the United States, ²³	2/4	The Amazon citizen science platform is exploring both types of collaboration.
Spanish citizen science platform Spanish citizen science observatory	Spain	4	The adoption of the code of EU-Citizen.Science is planned.
CS Track H2020 project	Austria, Belgium, Finland, Germany, Greece, Israel, Spain ²⁴	2	Both platforms have connected through the API and the CS Track project has pulled data on citizen science projects from EU-Citizen.Science to contribute to their work in building a citizen science evidence base.
Dutch citizen science platform	Netherlands	2	The Dutch platform is using WordPress for their national platform and would like to connect to EU-Citizen.Science using the API.
Ciência Viva	Portugal	2	The Portuguese platform is deciding on what platform they want to use (e.g. WordPress or other) and depending on that a plug-in to connect via the API and exchange projects in both directions is needed. The last release of the Platform will provide the multilingual support needed by the Portuguese platform.
Danish citizen science platform	Denmark	2	The Danish citizen science network has expressed interest in connecting via a plug-in with WordPress in the future.

²³ Citizen Science for the Amazon is a network of more than 25 civil society organizations, government entities, universities, research centers and foundations, individuals and other networks.

²⁴ These are the countries where the partners of the CS Track project are located.

Technical costs

As described in section 4.2 there are some technical tasks that need to be performed to maintain the Platform up and running without compromising security and efficiency. We consider these tasks as minimum technical requirements. All these tasks can be done in 100 hours or less (yearly) including fixing new bugs that might appear in the Platform (python code). Of course, the host server cost and the wildcard SSL certificate cost need to be included in the budget of the Sustainability Plan. The following table covers the yearly cost of the minimal actions needed to maintain the Platform online.

Table 4: Mandatory costs - calculated by Ibercivis

Host server:	Approx. 120 €/pa
Wildcard SSL Certificate ²⁵ :	Approx. 80 €/pa
100 hours (35 €/h) technical support ²⁶ :	3500 €/pa

5.2 Actions to sustain the EU-Citizen.Science Platform

This subsection brings together a list of concrete actions and recommendations to ensure Platform sustainability. Some actions can be implemented more immediately and for others more time and strategy is needed to initiate them (e.g. if they involve other parties and/or processes). The list of actions is pre-ordered according to what actions should be implemented first or prioritised to orientate the activities of ECSA on the Platform after the handover. The list of actions builds up²⁷ on the minimum Platform requirements, which are:

1. Keeping the community active and engaged (community engagement)
 - a. Approx. two hours per week of moderating community forums and addressing requests submitted via the contact form of the Platform (answering questions and connecting people)
2. Keeping the content fresh, timely and growing (moderation and community management)
 - a. Approx. two hours per week of moderating submitted projects, resources and training profiles for approval following the quality criteria framework and the established moderation process, and checking the events, organisations and platforms/networks submitted to check for spam or inappropriate uses of the Platform.

²⁵ This certificate can be used for subdomains (e.g. <https://moodle.eu-citizen.science>).

²⁶ Cost for maintenance (update of installed libraries and programs), bug solving, etc. We estimate that this number of hours will be sufficient to cover all annual needs.

²⁷ For the sake of simplicity, the minimal Platform requirements are repeated (but paraphrased) in the list of actions so the latter can function as an independent and complete guide.

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- b. Approx. two hours per week of actively reaching out to the wider citizen science community to involve them in the Platform, joining conversations and contributing content
 - c. Approx. one hour per week of actively checking what content needs updating and actively reaching out to content ‘owners’ (i.e. users that have submitted content to the Platform) to check and update their material
3. Keeping the Platform online and working (hosting and bug-fixing), as explained in section 4.2

The identified dimensions of the sustainability strategy have been included in table 5, next to the actions listed. The table indicates what dimensions of the strategy each action mainly contributes to. It should be pointed out that following the definition of exploitation provided in section 2.2 and the account of it given in section 4.2, almost all of the actions included in the list could be understood as contributing to exploitation. However, only actions that go beyond *using* and *maintaining* the Platform (and Project results) in the same way or in a very similar way as it has been done during the Project’s lifetime are marked as such.

Table 5: List of actions to sustain the EU-Citizen.Science platform

Action	Technical S.	Thematic S.	Financial S.	Engagement	Exploitation
Continue to accept the deposition of projects, resources and training resources on the Platform and moderate these submissions following the quality criteria framework and the procedure used during the Project. ECSA staff will ensure that these submissions have been deposited correctly. Events, organisations and platforms/networks submitted as well as comments posted in the forum will be moderated to check for spam or inappropriate uses of the Platform.		X			
Continue to answer requests sent via the contact form of the Platform and point people to the information and material they are looking for.				X	
Replace broken links. There is a high likelihood for some URLs to stop working or to change, and that will require updating the information on the Platform. This is expected following alerts from users who cannot find the information, since resources to proactively check that the links are still active are limited.		X			
ECSA staff will submit new content to the Platform. This includes the profiles of projects in which ECSA is involved, resources stemming from these projects and relevant resources and training resources.		X			
Improve site accessibility to be compliant with the WCAG 2.1 guidelines (https://www.w3.org/TR/WCAG21/).	X			X	

Action	Technical S.	Thematic S.	Financial S.	Engagement	Exploitation
Add a submission form for blog posts so users can submit posts to the blog in a similar way to submitting a project profile.		X		X	
ECSA has been using the events section on the Platform to showcase citizen science events, including linking to it in the ECSA newsletter and referring interested people to it and will continue to do so.		X		X	
<p>Continue to use the social media channels (especially the twitter account) of the Project.</p> <p>The social media channels of the Project build upon the work initiated by DITOs. During the Project, we have succeeded in developing the audience of the different channels and the social media channels now have an important place in the citizen science social media landscape. A possibility is to keep the twitter account as a general “news about citizen science” and “updates about the Platform”.</p> <p>It needs to be decided if the EU-Citizen.Science newsletter is incorporated into the newsletter of ECSA, which has almost three times its reach.</p>				X	X
<p>Continue the monthly SwafS citizen science meetings with RIA and EU-funded projects and identify synergies. ECSA will continue to provide the space and coordinate these meetings and a SwafS project will take over the moderation each month. This will be kicked-off before the end of the Project and a calendar for the first months of 2022 will be established.</p> <p>The active exchange with EU-funded SwafS projects will be useful to harness projects and (training) resources for the Platform.</p>		X		X	X
<p>Implement permanent virtual access points to online exploitable project results.</p> <p>The technical sustainability of the Platform and of the Moodle platform for training modules, and the fact that all Project deliverables are uploaded to Zenodo will ensure that exploitable project results can be disseminated.</p>					X
<p>Disseminate exploitable project results.</p> <p>All consortium partners are advised to support the dissemination of exploitable project results (see section 4.3) through their channels and tools, e.g. social media and the organisation’s website, during events by highlighting the benefits of the Platform.</p> <p>Both the training materials and the training modules will be promoted regularly to ECSA members, to people who are contacting the organisation with requests about training, and when new projects are planned. The project partners will also share the information about these resources and will use it in their own training and teaching.</p> <p>Deliverables produced during the Project that are relevant to the citizen science community will be submitted to the Platform as (training) resources.</p>					X

Action	Technical S.	Thematic S.	Financial S.	Engagement	Exploitation
Sign an MoU with other organisations that have linked their citizen science platforms to the Platform for accountability and endorsement of our endeavour.	X			X	
Continue to link the Platform to other citizen science platforms and foster interoperability between them and EU-Citizen.Science. The future of the Platform lies partly in providing ways to decline itself at national levels while maintaining a European coordination and visibility.	X				
Create a working group within ECSA to maintain the Platform. One of ECSA's greatest assets are its members and working groups that can significantly contribute content to the Platform, and help maintain communication channels active and engaging. ECSA HQ will propose the creation of a working group focussing on the Platform and involving members interested in the Platform as a way to move this process forward. ECSA members represent all sectors of society and therefore this would ensure that all relevant stakeholders are engaged and connected. The newly created ECSA WG could organise the webinars and meetings mentioned in this list of actions.	X	X	X	X	X
Organise a meeting with ECSA HQ and the ECSA Board at the beginning of 2022 to assign short-term responsibilities to specific staff members and define an interval to check the development of these tasks and to implement further actions from the Sustainability Plan.	X	X	X	X	X
Regularly evaluate Platform access statistics. Examine Google Analytics, ideally monthly but at least once every three months to understand what users are looking at and where they are spending most of their time (i.e. Are Platform users spending time where we would like or expect them to spend it?). Evaluate if the numbers reflect our actions and aims and adjust ²⁸ .	X	X		X	
Encourage the creators of training modules to keep ownership and update the content of their material. The 20 training modules created on the Moodle platform will need updating of URLs and information to ensure that they continue to provide an appropriate user experience. This will be done by ECSA staff contacting the module creators once a year, to suggest to them to check and update their module.		X			

²⁸ Example: We might put a lot of time and effort in a content or page that we would like users to go to. If this is not happening, we could boost promotion of that page via social media and refer users to it by placing it in a more visible place (adding a link to it to the homepage). If users then access this content more often but leave the page quickly and/or do not interact with it, this would be a sign that users are not really interested in that content.

Action	Technical S.	Thematic S.	Financial S.	Engagement	Exploitation
Showcase how many people are following a project, have bookmarked a resource, etc. to get more Platform users to do that and build their own list of favourite content to refer to. The goal is also to create benefits for users who actively contribute to the Platform.	X			X	
Set up new training modules on Moodle and coordinate the development of new training modules (e.g. make the module design guidelines available to course developers and give them the rights to be able to edit in Moodle).		X			
Exploit the training modules for paid-for training sessions that will use the material on the Platform as a source of funding. While the training modules are designed for self-learning without a tutor, they have the potential to run as part of a tutor guided session. These sessions will be offered by ECSA and a tutor for a fee and will be promoted widely. They can run in different countries and will provide an income that will assist supporting the upkeep of the EU-Citizen.Science platform. ECSA could do the promotion and management of payment, and the people who created the content or are willing to teach people using it would mostly dedicate their time for delivery. The income from such an effort would be split between ECSA and the trainer. This could be an incentive for ECSA members to engage with HQ. An enhanced certificate could be offered to participants in the session.			X		X
Get feedback from the community before doing big changes to the Platform. Use events or workshops organised by ECSA and/or where the Platform is presented as an opportunity to ask participants for feedback on new Platform developments in planning. This could avoid spending time and effort on things that will not provide much value to the community of users on the Platform and therefore, to the Platform itself.	X	X		X	
Stimulate local networks at national level to get people to translate content on the Platform so it can reach and draw the attention of more people, i.e. potential future users. Until the end of the Project almost all static Platform content will be translated into the 11 European languages represented in the consortium. The final release of the Platform will incorporate the option for the community of users to submit translations of the descriptions in projects, resources, etc. (multi-language support).		X		X	
Provide new projects with a checklist of what the platform offers (forum, blog...) and express an expectation that projects use the Platform besides listing their project.		X		X	
Organise regular events to actively engage with the community.				X	

Action	Technical S.	Thematic S.	Financial S.	Engagement	Exploitation
Organise webinars on a regular basis to present the Platform to ECSA members and the wider citizen science community to engage them in using the Platform, submitting new content and providing feedback.				X	
Implement training and capacity building workshops. These events – either organised by consortium partners or organised by others, where consortium partners will participate – are a great opportunity to present the Platform and Project results, especially the citizen science projects, resources, training resources and training modules on the Platform, and share them directly with interested stakeholders.				X	X
Foster synergies with different initiatives. Partnerships and synergies created during the Project should be maintained (e.g. the monthly SwafS meetings and local networks or meetings of the Project partners with local contacts) to continue using and sharing (i.e. exploiting) the Platform and expanding the Platform’s user base. Make sure to communicate directly or indirectly (via social media, newsletter, and mailing lists), with initiatives with which contact should be maintained.				X	X
Organise regular meetings with other international citizen science networks to share with them the Platform and project results that they could find useful, e.g. the quality criteria framework for resources. Alternatively use an already planned meeting as an opportunity to do that. Continue to establish synergies with them to help in translating key documents.				X	X
Promote the project results of a project that is soon ending (via social media, the Platform, a blog post, list the project events in the event section) in exchange of that project submitting a project profile (or updating their already existing project profile) and the resources/results produced during that project.		X		X	
Offer Platform space to ECSA WG as documentation of events. Encourage WG to produce interactive material to introduce the work done in the group.		X		X	
Ensure the sustainability of finalised citizen science projects by hosting citizen science project websites once the projects have ended against a small fee.	X		X		
Set up a metadata system to help linking to other platforms.	X				
Offer microservices to build the community of developers. This involves thinking how to split the code (into modules), using a docker, offering an easy way to personalise the frontend (so other projects can more easily use the code), maintaining the code and facilitating the introduction to it.	X			X	
Apply knowledge and best practice in EU-Citizen.Science to other (EU-funded) projects.					X

Action	Technical S.	Thematic S.	Financial S.	Engagement	Exploitation
The aim is the transfer of knowledge, skills and best practices from the Project to other projects and initiatives in which partners in the consortium are (going to be) involved. Scaling and replicating Project results both avoids reinventing the wheel and disseminates and promotes the Project and the Platform.					
Get an agreement with the JRC that we closely link their work with the Platform and also that Horizon Research make it a requirement that all EU funded citizen science projects must link with the Platform.		X			
Create links for the development of EU-wide projects. e.g.: foster collaboration between already existing projects on the same topic or similar topics, which are merged into a unique solution with the help of platform facilities, sharing tools, solutions and results.				X	
Projects with little funding and regions with a less widespread citizen science approach are supported with expertise and, if possible, resources. Advantages of the broad network of experts are used to develop EU-level solutions that provide visibility and impact across the continent.			X	X	
Organise targeted workshops with key advocates to further citizen science in research and universities: ECSA WG on citizen science and universities , INCENTIVE project on building four citizen science hubs across Europe, COESO project and their landscape study, and the TIME4CS project on embedding citizen science in research institutions.				X	
Contact and connect with relevant Open Science advocates, platforms and communities. Send them a manifestation of interest.				X	
Build an operating reserve that totals six months of operating costs.			X		
Expand the membership and donor base of ECSA.			X		
Seek multiple grants simultaneously. Being open source ECSA may submit to calls for improvement of the Platform provided that these improvements are published under the same license. It will continue to be regulated under the EUPL license.			X		
Create a section with news on the Platform that allows users to quickly post updates from projects.	X	X			
ECSA as well as organisations that depend on the Platform code may apply to get (national) microfunding to keep developing the Platform together - in a 'federated system'.	X		X		
Propose paid-for training and courses on the integration of citizen science into policies to policy makers and administrations. Link with ministries or administration departments, policy and cabinet advisers to ensure the			X		X

Action	Technical S.	Thematic S.	Financial S.	Engagement	Exploitation
implementation of citizen science approaches in policies. The Platform could become the key reference and expert hub for policy makers. Project deliverables developed under WP4 will be particularly promoted towards these stakeholders.					
Hire a consultant to help with long-term planning.			X		
Review different funding models and propose a long-term funding model.			X		
Develop resources aligned with the hot topics/trends of the moment.		X		X	

Handover to ECSA

Before the end of the year and of the Project, there will be a handover of documents and information to ECSA so that ECSA staff has obtained all relevant information and can continue to carry out the processes and tasks that should be maintained from 2022. Examples of information and documents included in this handover go from the log-in details to all social media accounts, to ensuring that ECSA staff has access to all documents (in an editable format) that are needed to maintain the Platform and its content (e.g. module design guidelines to develop training modules in Moodle), over to ensuring that ECSA staff members receive relevant automated Platform emails and have the contact details of relevant partners and organisations (e.g. contact details of all training module developers to encourage them to update the content of the training modules they have produced).

Challenges and threats in implementing the Sustainability Plan

As with any plan, ECSA might face certain challenges in implementing the Sustainability Plan and the recommended actions in the table above. ECSA has ensured that the minimum Platform requirements described at the beginning of section 5.2 will be fulfilled. However, once the Project funding ends, ECSA might encounter a lack of both financial and human resources to be able to carry out many more additional actions recommended in the list. Part of the Sustainability Plan and strategy is to prioritise and deliberately decide to focus on some issues over others; the pre-ordered list of actions provided may simplify the activities of ECSA on the Platform after the handover. Involving the ECSA members and the broader citizen science community will be key in addressing and mitigating the lack of human resources. Moreover, ECSA might need to overcome language barriers to ensure equal access to Platform content to the target audience. The final release of the Platform includes multi-language support, which incorporates the option for the community of users to submit translations of the descriptions in projects, (training) resources, etc. This

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functionality paired together with the fact that the *ECSA Ten Principles of Citizen Science*²⁹ have been translated into 30 languages by the citizen science community and that this community can thus be activated, are reasons to believe that this challenge can be overcome. Finally, the vision and mission of ECSA and of the Platform nicely overlap and complement each other. With the Platform, ECSA directly complies with and fulfils the association's statutes. The Platform is ECSA and ECSA is the Platform and with it part of the association's purpose is fulfilled. They will be – and to a large extent already are – thought together. Therefore, actions carried out to realise ECSA's vision and to advocate for the mainstreaming of citizen science in Europe and for building a strong citizen science community will be aligned with necessary actions to maintain the Platform and will include it as *the* European reference point and central knowledge hub. Hence, not all necessary actions to maintain the Platform will start from scratch; a lot of work is being done already. This is another argument for overcoming a lack of human resources.

6 Conclusion

This deliverable presents the Sustainability Plan for the EU-Citizen.Science platform and the path followed to develop this plan. The main elements of the Sustainability Plan are the results of the collective reflection, cross-cutting recommendations, five dimensions of sustainability, the legacy of the EU-Citizen.Science project and its exploitation, and most importantly, a pre-ordered list of recommended actions. However, it is important to mention that the journey to make the EU-Citizen.Science platform sustainable, especially in terms of technical and thematic sustainability, started at the beginning with the project concept, and continued with each step in the planning and development of the Platform over the last almost three years.

The core mission of the Platform is to be *the European reference point for citizen science through cross-network knowledge sharing for citizen science participants, practitioners, researchers, policy makers and society across Europe*. Since the launch of the first version of the Platform in April 2020, over 48.000 users have visited the Platform – a huge success. The aim now is to maintain the Platform and allow it to develop through and with the community.

To ensure the best possible development of the Platform in the coming months and years, this Sustainability Plan will serve as a roadmap to guide ECSA when it takes over the administration, maintenance and development of the Platform after the project is completed. The development of the Platform will remain dynamic and subject to change to reflect on the future needs of the community. This roadmap is intended to be a guide that will be reflected upon and reviewed with the community to ensure that it remains relevant to the community's current needs as ECSA takes on this responsibility.

The vision and mission of ECSA and the Platform align and complement each other, and many of the actions that ECSA carries out to advance citizen science in Europe and contribute to the

²⁹ ECSA (European Citizen Science Association). 2015. Ten Principles of Citizen Science. Berlin. <http://doi.org/10.17605/OSF.IO/XPR2N>. Available at: <https://zenodo.org/record/5127534#.YWVXcN9CSUI>

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democratisation of science have been giving and will continue to give visibility to the Platform. This effort, together with the Sustainability Plan are good instruments to address the challenge at hand. The Sustainability Strategy provides a vision to look forward towards the future of the Platform and think more broadly about ways of sustaining it and is complemented by the Sustainability Action Plan, which formulates concrete recommendations for action that are pre-ordered to orientate ECSA's actions from the start. To implement the Sustainability Plan and realise the Platform's mission ECSA will engage with its members, the broader citizen science community and relevant stakeholders. Still, it is paramount that the partners that have made this Platform possible continue to use and share it – especially considering their role as co-creators of the Platform.

The EU-Citizen.Science platform is a great achievement that gives the citizen science community and interested stakeholders the opportunity to use it and to expand its value through their use as well as to participate in its further development. The creation and development of the Platform in the last three years has brought it to the point where it is capable of serving as a European Hub and continues to grow. ECSA will take this opportunity to maintain and build up the Platform and guarantee that it lives on, stays lively and develops to the best for the community – through co-creation with the community.

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